

Annex 6

Risk assessment, design, and implementation of biosecurity programs in farm

Farm-specific Action Plans

Example 1. Extensive livestock (bovine and pigs)

Example 2. Intensive pig production

Example 3. Poultry: layers

SABIO
Sanidad y Biotecnología
Health and Biotechnology

World Organisation
for Animal Health

Annex 6

Example 1

Risk assessment, design, and implementation of biosecurity programs in extensive livestock farm

Farm-specific Action Plan

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This real example has been developed by Health and Biotechnology Group of the National Institute on Wildlife Research (IREC) of the University of Castile-La Mancha/CSIC/JCCM and University of Córdoba.

Index

Risk assessment, design, and implementation of biosecurity programs against tuberculosis in extensive livestock farm in Extremadura (Spain)

1. Basics of tuberculosis

Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex

Routes of infection of the *Mycobacterium Complex tuberculosis*

Persistence of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex in the environment

Importance of the interaction between wildlife and livestock

2. Biosecurity programs in extensive livestock farms: Farm-specific Action Plan

National Tuberculosis Eradication Program

Biosecurity programs: a complementary approach

Methodology

3. Description of the specific biosecurity program for the livestock farm

Livestock description and risk identification

General characteristics and management of livestock

Presence of wildlife and game management

Map

Risk points of interaction between livestock and wildlife

Proposed biosecurity measures in livestock farming: general and specific

Health management and control of livestock movements

Game management

Management of enclosures and fences

Water point management

Pasture management

Management of carrion and livestock by-products

4. Conclusions

5. Acknowledgments

6. Contact

7. Annexes

Sheet of actions implemented in the farm

Photographic archive

Improvement of commercial type drinking trough for cattle

Selective drinking fountain model for pigs

1. Basics of tuberculosis

Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex

Animal tuberculosis (TB) is a chronic disease caused by mycobacteria of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex*, which affects a wide variety of domestic and wild species. This disease is subject to control in developed countries due to its implications for animal health, public health, and the management and conservation of wildlife.

In Spain, TB is present in cattle, goats, pigs, and, occasionally, sheep. While cattle are considered the main natural domestic reservoir of the disease, other species may also play an important role in its epidemiology. Thus, there is evidence of significant distribution, even high prevalence of TB, in free-range pig farming in the center and south of the country. In addition to these domestic reservoirs, four wild species are known in Spain that can act as reservoirs: wild boar, red deer, and, to a lesser extent, fallow deer and badger, the latter in northern Spain.

Routes of infection of the Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex

In cattle, TB primarily affects the respiratory tract, so the main route of transmission may be the exchange of respiratory secretions or aerosols. Infected goats tend to develop cavernous lung lesions, similar to those seen in humans. These species, as well as pigs, can also become infected by ingesting food (feed, grass, etc.) or water contaminated with mycobacteria from other infected animals. Therefore, the possible routes of mycobacteria excretion in these species are multiple and include, in addition to the direct respiratory route, an indirect route through saliva, feces, and urine.

Among wild species in Spain, wild boar has one of the highest prevalences of TB worldwide (sometimes exceeding 50%). As in domestic pigs, lesions primarily affect the lymph nodes of the head, with lesions frequently found simultaneously in other anatomical regions, such as the lungs. Consequently, oronasal excretion is highly significant in wild boar, affecting up to 20% of the population. Furthermore, considering fecal excretion, the proportion of excreting individuals can increase to 33%. Therefore, the risk of environmental contamination by this species is very high in its range and is proportional to its abundance. In red deer and fallow deer, the prevalence of infected animals is usually lower (usually between 10% and 20%, although locally it can reach 50%), and the distribution of lesions does not show a clear anatomical pattern. Therefore, deer can excrete through different routes, contaminating pastures, feed, soil, and water. It should not be forgotten that, locally, deer may be more abundant than wild boar, and in that case, they could pose as much or even greater risk of TB transmission to livestock. Badgers, on the other hand, have very low abundances in Mediterranean Spain. Therefore, although they can be infected, they are not, in principle, as epidemiologically relevant as ungulates, at least in central and southern Spain.

Persistence of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex in the environment

Environmental contamination with bacteria of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex may play a very important role in the spread of TB through indirect transmission, that is, without requiring direct contact between infected and susceptible animals. The survival of mycobacteria in the environment can vary, according to different studies, from a few days to more than 300 days depending on temperature, humidity, exposure to sunlight, and the amount of organic matter in the substrate. In a previous study conducted in two livestock-raising regions in central and southern Spain, the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex was identified in more than 50% of mud samples from the periphery of ponds and in 10% of water samples analyzed, suggesting a high level of persistence in the environment. No mycobacteria were detected in elevated water troughs inaccessible to wild boar.

Importance of the interaction between wildlife and livestock

Human intervention in the territory, both through livestock and hunting, facilitates direct (physical or very close) or indirect (use of the same areas, but at different times) contact between livestock and wildlife. These interactions facilitate the transmission of pathogens. In general, dry pastoral systems predominate in the central and southern Iberian Peninsula, where livestock and wildlife share pastures and water. It has been observed that direct contact between these species tends to be much less frequent than indirect contact, so in the case of TB, the indirect transmission route is the main one.

Currently, extensive livestock farming can hardly compete economically with intensive livestock farming. Therefore, any factor affecting the profitability of extensive systems, such as diseases that find their reservoir in wild species, particularly impacts their future and economic sustainability. Furthermore, maintaining adequate livestock numbers is essential to ensure the conservation of the dehesa (savannah-like habitats with oaks) and the biodiversity of flora and fauna.

In central and southern Spain, wild ungulate populations are rapidly expanding, primarily due to their use for hunting. Wild boar is currently the most widespread and abundant species. The two cervid species involved, red deer and fallow deer, are widely distributed, especially red deer, with high densities at the local level. Significant spatial associations have been observed between the high density of these species and the incidence of TB in livestock. Available scientific information suggests that infection in wild ungulates hampers TB control in livestock species in central and southern Spain.

Our research group has quantified contact rates between wild and domestic ungulates in Mediterranean ecosystems, revealing a high risk of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex transmission at water sources, where the highest number of interactions between these species has been detected. These results suggest that reducing the rate of interspecies contact, especially at water sources, would impact the control of pathogen transmission, such as mycobacteria and *Brucella. suis*, or the Aujeszky's Disease or African Swine Fever viruses.

2. Biosecurity programs in extensive livestock farms

National Tuberculosis Eradication Program

The implementation of biosecurity programs on extensive livestock farms against wildlife has been around for a relatively recent time in Spain and has focused almost exclusively on TB. The first TB control measures in Spain began in the early 1950s, and in 1987, Spain introduced an Accelerated Eradication Program for cattle in accordance with EU Directives. Currently, the ultimate goal of the Program is the eradication of the disease, defined as achieving less than 0.1% of infected cattle herds per year for six consecutive years, and ensuring that at least 99.9% of herds are officially free of the disease during those six consecutive years. This Program, implemented by the Autonomous Communities, has laid the foundation for increasing diagnostic sensitivity, both at the herd and individual levels. Its compliance and implementation, especially its diagnosis, constitute the cornerstone of TB eradication on livestock farms in our country. However, the Program is not implemented in a similar manner for other domestic reservoirs, such as goats, where only certain herds are monitored, or pigs, where it is limited to an epidemiological surveillance system in slaughterhouses; in both cases, whenever these species are suspected of being involved in TB outbreaks in cattle.

When uncontrolled domestic and wild reservoirs contribute to maintaining the infection, the Program's conventional measures are insufficient to provide effective TB control at this domestic-wild interface. Biosecurity programs on extensive livestock farms are additional measures gradually introduced to manage newly identified risks, such as those emanating from these types of reservoirs. These biosecurity programs are essential in settings such as the Extremaduran dehesa, where the entry route for both TB and other infectious diseases (Aujeszky's disease, Hepatitis E, Porcine Brucellosis, Trichinellosis, and African Swine Fever) into herds can originate from wild species. The livestock, hunting, and health sectors must work together, as only a comprehensive strategy to combat shared pathogens makes sense to minimize the risks of transmission in these settings.

In Spain, the TB Eradication Program has reduced the proportion of positive cattle herds from almost 20% in the 1970s to less than 2% in the last decade. However, the distribution of positive animals is uneven (Figure 1), with a high herd prevalence remaining in regions of the South-Central and Western parts of the country (17.1% in Andalusia, 13.0% in Extremadura, and 7.9% in Castilla-La Mancha in 2016; data from the 2018 National TB Eradication Program (MAPA). Within these regions, there is a higher risk of TB persistence on extensive farms, often facilitated by contact between the various domestic and wild reservoirs. In this regard, a recent study conducted on extensive pig farming and wild boar in Andalusia detected seropositive individuals in 24.8% and 78.2% of the farms and hunting grounds analyzed, respectively.

Figure 1. Prevalence of TB in cattle herds. National TB Eradication Program (MAPA, 2018).

Biosecurity programs: a complementary approach

Biosecurity on a livestock farm consists of a set of preventive measures and standards designed to maintain control over risk factors arising from biological, physical, or chemical agents, thereby preventing harmful impacts from risks inherent in daily operations. Preventive measures in areas where livestock and wildlife interact have the essential objective of reducing or avoiding interactions between livestock, wildlife, and the environment. To this end, various actions can be recommended, ranging from management changes to major investments in physical or deterrent barriers.

On cattle farms in the United Kingdom, the use of simple exclusion measures, when properly applied, was 100% effective in preventing badger entry into farm buildings, potentially contributing to reducing the transmission of mycobacteria between badgers and cattle. In Riding Mountain National Park (Canada), local fencing was successfully combined with the use of sheepdogs, among other measures, to reduce the risk of TB transmission between deer and cattle. Furthermore, a specific biosecurity program targeting wild ungulates (deer and wild boar) was evaluated for the first time on an extensive cattle farm in the Alcudia Valley (Ciudad Real, Spain), with very promising results (Figures 2 and 3). Thus, due to the specificities of each situation, each farm must be specifically assessed to determine which measures may be effective in preventing contact between different species, both domestic and wild. Therefore, each biosecurity program must be integrated with the measures established in the National TB Eradication Program, in addition to being:

- Effective: should minimize direct/indirect contact between livestock and wildlife.
- Practical: it must be feasible for the farmer.
- Realistic: You must minimize risks as much as possible, since they cannot be eliminated 100%.

Figure 2. Different approaches to making aggregation points “cattle-only permeable” or “wild ungulate-only permeable” are illustrated. (A) Ungulate-proof fence at “pond-type watering trough”, (B) “cattle-proof fence” suitable for deer (jumping) and with steps for sheep, (C) “wildlife-proof gate”, (D) ground-level step suitable for wild boar, (E) brush at “wildlife-proof gate” activated by a cattle pushing on an arm armed with a brush, (F) selective opening for roe deer (and potentially scratches) (18 cm wide, 60 cm high frame) at “cattle-proof fence”.

Figure 3. The data show a downward trend in TB incidence (expressed as a percentage) in cattle (black line) after separating cattle from wildlife at watering points through the implementation of a targeted biosecurity program. On neighboring farms where no intervention was implemented (gray line), TB incidence remained at the same levels (even with some increase) as before the intervention on the study farm.

The objective of this Farm-specific biosecurity plan is to provide technical advice for mitigating TB risks by designing and implementing a customized program of specific biosecurity actions for each extensive livestock farm.

Extensive pig production in the Iberian Peninsula and farm selection

Iberian pigs (and crossbreeds) are typically linked to the southwestern quadrant of Spain (and adjacent areas of Portugal). The production of these animals constitutes a professional and commercial sector (not a backyard system) in which they are mainly raised under extensive conditions. In recent decades, the traditional extensive pig sector has undergone a profound transformation, leading to a great diversity of farming systems. The tendency on more professional farms is to differentiate between production stages (breeding-gestation, lactation-weaning, growing, and fattening). Enclosed housing, with little or no access to the outside, is used for sows and piglets until weaning (up to 23 kg). During the growing period (up to 110 kg), the piglets are usually reared on dehesa pasture connected to open buildings or feeding paddocks. The final fattening phase (up to 160–185 kg), known as the montanera/mast (pigs feed on acorns outside), starts in autumn when the pigs remain outdoors in the dehesa to feed on acorns and grass. Nevertheless, traditional farrow-to-finish farms, small commercial farms (< 25 fatteners and < 5 sows) and non-commercial family farms (< 5 fatteners for self-consumption) continue to be prominent despite the transformation in the extensive sector. In this farm, Iberian pig have access to the outdoor area in the dehesa (outdoor pig farms).

Methodology

The phases into which this work is divided are (Figure 4):

1. Specific prior study of each livestock farm.
 - i) Obtaining general background information.
 - ii) TB History:
 - Bovine: official veterinary control.
 - Extensive pig farming: sampling and laboratory analysis.
 - Wildlife (wild boar and deer): sampling during hunts and laboratory analysis.
 - iii) Mapping.
2. Specific visit to each farm.
 - i) Personal interview with the farmer/manager: epidemiological survey:
 - General characteristics of the farm.
 - Livestock management.
 - Game management.
 - Georeferencing of uses and management.
 - Identification of potential risk points.
 - ii) *On-site* field study:
 - Individual description of each risk point: measures and fauna indications.
 - Environmental sampling (mud).
 - Taking graphic documentation (photographs).
3. Design and implementation of the specific biosecurity program: "First report: risk assessment and proposed measures" (**delivered here**).
 - i) Health management and control of livestock movements.
 - ii) Game and wildlife management.
 - iii) Management of enclosures and fences.
 - iv) Water point management.
 - v) Pasture management.
 - vi) Management of carrion and livestock by-products.
4. Monitoring: verification and evaluation of the implementation of proposed measures.
 - i) Receipt of the annex "sheet of implemented actions".
 - ii) New field visit:
 - Environmental sampling (mud).
 - Taking graphic documentation (photographs).
 - iii) Longitudinal evaluation of TB outcomes: pre- and post-program implementation:
 - Bovine: official veterinary control.
 - Extensive pig farming: laboratory analysis.
 - Wildlife: laboratory analysis.
 - Cost evaluation.

Figure 4. Work methodology and schedule.

3. Description of the specific biosecurity program for livestock farm “Example for WOA”

Description of the livestock

General characteristics and management of livestock

Table 1. General farm data.

Name	Example for WOA
Code	xxxxxxxx
Municipality	Anywhere in Extremadura (Spain)
contact person	Farmer Jhon Deere
Post	In charge
Phone	xxxxx
E-mail	Xxx@es

Table 2. Description of the farm: 09/26/2024

Total area	650 hectares
Area dedicated to livestock farming	520 hectares
Surface used by pigs	310 hectares
Percentage of pastureland	100%
Percentage of forest	0%
Pig farming system	Priming + Montanera (montanera is the mast season, pigs feed on acorns outdoor during winter for final fattening)
Breed	Crossed
Heads	Priming: 1360 Montanera: 160
Lots	Priming: 3 Montanera: 2 (can be subdivided into 2 additional)
Feeding	Priming: commercial flour and silage Montanera: acorn and feed
History of TB	Priming Input: NEGATIVE Priming Exit-Montanera Entrance: NEGATIVE Montanera Exit: POSITIVE
BOVINE exploitation system	Extensive (owned)

Breed	Blanca Cacereña, Avileña and Charolais
Heads	150
Lots	2 lots: Cacereñas-Charolais and Avileñas-Charolais
Feeding	Environmental
History of TB	Historically negative. Intermittent positivity at other farms in the region. First positive result in 2018 (Cacereñas)
SHEEP PRODUCTION SYSTEM	There is no
Goat exploitation system	There is no
OTHER domestic species	6 dogs, 2 cats and 2 horses
HUNTING MANAGEMENT	The farms is also a big game hunting private reserve
Perimeter bordering big game hunting reserves	100%
Big game hunting bag	15 wild boars and 5 deer per season
Feeding	Some years they have baited (corn) before the hunting drive and, more commonly, for small game (dove).
History of TB	Unknown. Negative in 2017-2018 (10 wild boars)

This farm is an extensive mixed pig and cattle farm with some simultaneous agricultural use. It is fenced for big game hunting, although there is no particular interest in this use. The farm is crossed by a local road which links the two towns, in an environment made up of similar types of farms (see map). To the north and west, the agricultural type stands out, mainly dedicated to cereal crops, while to the east and south, extensive livestock raised in the pastureland predominates. The mountain area, a potential refuge for wild ungulates, is located very close to the farm, to the east.

All of the farm's fences, both the perimeter and the internal enclosures, are livestock-grade. Their state of maintenance is acceptable for livestock management, but deficient from a biosecurity perspective against wild species. In fact, during the visit, we identified a wild boar scab in one of the yearling plots, included in one of the yearling herds. The livestock fencing is highest in the plots bordering the road, in plot C14, where the main livestock facilities are located, and in some specific sections of the perimeter fence.

Table 3. Subdivision of the farm. The same identifiers as on the map are used.

PARCEL	LAND USE	OBSERVATIONS
C1	<u>Livestock</u> : Cacereño cattle breed + Montanera pigs	Longer montanera time
C2	<u>Agricultural</u> : Sowing	No livestock
C3	<u>Facilities</u> : E1 (Housing)	No livestock
C4	<u>Livestock</u> : Cacereño cattle + Montanera pigs	
C5	<u>Livestock</u> : Cacereño cattle + Montanera pigs	
C6	<u>Livestock</u> : Cacereño cattle + Montanera pigs	
C7	<u>Livestock</u> : Cacereño cattle + Montanera pigs	
C8	<u>Cattle rancher</u> : Cacereño cattle	"Confinement" plot
C9	<u>Cattle rancher</u> : Cacereño cattle	"Confinement" plot
C10	<u>Cattle</u> : Avilanian cattle breed	"Confinement" plot
C11	<u>Cattle rancher</u> : Priming (small lots) + Montanera	Without cattle

C12	<u>Cattle</u> : Priming (medium lot) + Montanera	Without cattle
C13	<u>Cattle rancher</u> : Priming (large lots) + Montanera	Without cattle
C14	<u>Facilities</u> : Orchard, cattle ranch*, primate center	Without cattle*
C15	<u>Cattle rancher</u> : Priming (nursing lot)	No cattle, occasional use
C16	<u>Livestock</u> : Avilanian cattle breed + Montanera pigs	Avilanian bovine breed herd
C17	<u>Livestock</u> : Avilanian cattle breed + Montanera pigs	Without water point
C18	<u>Agricultural</u> : Olive grove	No livestock

Pig production is divided into two clearly differentiated phases: yearling and montanera. The yearling, rearing or transition phase (March-October) takes place in specific facilities (yearling center; E3) associated with three outdoor plots, enabled for the different batches established based on weight. Throughout this phase, the yearlings are fed commercial meal in the concrete yards of E3, where they have sufficient low commercial or concrete drinkers (B E3). As they grow, the animals access the outdoor plots (C11-C13) to stimulate their environmental intake capacity and facilitate the transition to montanera. In each of these plots there are new drinkers of a similar type (Bp) and a pond or mud pit (X11-X13). The montanera, or end of fattening (November-February), takes place in certain plots on both sides of the road (not all; see Table 3), with rotational management in two batches depending on the availability of feed and water. During this phase (montanera), the animals are fed acorns and commercial feed in pellets (spread in a line on the ground of the plot where they are located) and are watered at the various water points available in each plot (ponds or streams—see map—or temporary water points caused by rain).

There are three distinct breeds of cattle permanently present on the farm: the Blanca Cacereña breed, which adds genetic and conservation value to the farm, and the Avileña breed, both kept in purity to obtain industrial crossbreeding with Charolais stallions. The Cacereña and Avileña breeds use different plots throughout the year (see Table 3), and the Charolais are not exchanged between lots. The Cacereño cattle are owned by the farm, while the Avileño cattle belong to a tenant who keeps a third of the animals permanently on the farm and incorporates the remaining two thirds into the lot to take advantage of the spring pastures (they then leave). In general, no commercial supplementary feed is provided, nor are there any specific drinkers for this species other than the one located in C8 (Bb).

Livestock management is geared toward minimizing direct contact between pigs and cattle. However, it is not entirely adequate to prevent indirect interactions between them, or potential interactions between the latter and wildlife. During the pig-feeding period, contact can only occur through the fence or, occasionally, if the animals (yearlings, cattle, or wild animals) manage to cross it. During the montanera period, pigs occupy plots normally used by cattle, as well as the grazing plots of yearlings. Furthermore, although cattle are confined to certain plots (see Table 3) two or three weeks before the start of the montanera period and remain confined until its end, this species is introduced into the montanera plots immediately after the pigs leave. Thus, pigs, cattle, and wild ungulates can use the same watering points in a relatively short period of time, with the consequent risk of transmitting shared pathogens. Table

8 provides a detailed analysis of the different points and risks of interaction identified in this farm

This farm is historically free of TB in cattle. However, the official 2018 sanitation campaign detected, for the first time, the presence of animals that react (Cacereño cattle) to diagnostic techniques, losing their T3 status. It is important to highlight that the cattle are replaced internally, so excluding the stallions, which are replaced periodically (the last addition was in 2015), and the "seasonal" Avileño cattle, there are no more cows from outside the farm. Therefore, the TB outbreak in cattle could have originated from interactions with other domestic or wild reservoirs. In this regard, the absence of any reproductive phase in pigs implies the annual introduction of more than 1,300 animals from outside the farm. Of these, only 160 pigs complete their cycle on the farm (montanera). Knowing the TB status of all these animals could minimize the potential risk of infection via this route, both on the farm itself and on the destination farms. Tables 4 and 5 show the TB serological status monitoring of this species during the 2017-2018 season, carried out by our research group within the framework of this study. The sample size was determined to detect the disease with a minimum prevalence of 2.0% and a 95.0% confidence interval.

Table 4. TB serological results (ELISA) at the breeding centre, both at the entrance and exit. Origin of breeding animals: EXTERNAL (Other region from Spain).

WEANING CENTER	Total number of animals	Number of animals sampled	Positives ELISA	Antibody prevalence (%)
Entrance	1200	150	0	0
Exit	1200	150	0	0

Table 5. Serological results of TB (ELISA) in pigs during free-range pig farming, sampled at the slaughterhouse at the time of slaughter. Origin of pigs: WEANING NUCLEUS.

MONTANERA	Total number of animals	Number of animals sampled	Positives ELISA	Antibody prevalence (%)	Lesions compatible with TB
Slaughterhouse	310	50	2	4.0	YES

The TB diagnostic results indicate that the yearlings had not had contact with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex bacteria* on their farms of origin, and that there was no circulation of mycobacteria during the yearling phase on the farm itself. However, the seroconversion of pigs at the end of the montanera period suggests that wild reservoirs could be involved in the transmission of mycobacteria to pigs, and probably also to cattle, since these are from shared-use plots.

Presence of wildlife and game management

Wild ungulates are commonly sighted on the farm, with wild boar being more common than deer (Table 6). According to farmers, wild boar is more abundant in the eastern and western extremes, which correspond to the areas furthest from the road (with less vehicle traffic) and more scrubby, especially to the east (where they have a larger refuge area). However, in times of scarcity of food or water, they can be seen in more central plots, where the main stream (XB) runs alongside the road and is temporarily baited with grain to attract turtledoves or wood pigeons for hunting purposes. In contrast, the frequency of deer sightings is more limited, and they can be seen anywhere on the farm.

The badger (*Meles meles*), on the other hand, is a difficult species to spot due to its nocturnal habits. However, there are several burrows with signs of constant use on the farm, especially in the central plots near XB.

Table 6. Frequency of wildlife detection.

Species	Presence				
	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Very sporadic	Never
Wild boar					
Red deer					
Fallow deer					
Badger					

Most of the region's properties are included in big game hunting reserves. However, the absence of large forest areas and the shared use of the territory with agricultural and livestock production systems make it difficult to conduct wild game drives or large drives for hunting wild ungulates. This situation limits the possibilities of extracting wild boar to hooking, small drives, or waiting, while deer hunting requires specific authorizations. For this reason, the game reserve indicated in Table 2, which refers to the total number of animals shot during each hunting season, is quite variable. Although the area being hunted is located outside the farm, it is consistent with the frequency of sightings of these species in the farm. Although corn has occasionally been used to concentrate wild boar in the area before hunting, there is no history of feed supplementation or waiting on the farm. Additionally, given the role that wild ungulates can play in the epidemiology of TB and the lack of specific data in the region, assessing and monitoring the TB status of these species would be very interesting to understand the risk of infection of livestock species via this route. Table 7 shows the TB diagnostic results obtained by our research group, within the framework of the present study, in wild boars shot during the 2017-2018 season. The absence of contact with bacteria of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex* could be associated with the age of the animals, since all of them were young or subadult individuals. Unlike the pigs, the sample size corresponded to all the specimens shot during the hunting day. These results suggest, with a 95% confidence level, that the prevalence of TB in wild boars in the reserve is less than 30%. It will be necessary to increase the sample size in successive campaigns to confirm these results.

Table 7. Results of TB diagnosis in wild boars shot on 10/22/2017.

Spp.	Number of animals sampled	Positives ELISA	Prevalence of antibodies against the <i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex</i>	Lesions compatible with TB
Wild boar	10	0	0%	NO

Map of the farm, indicating plots, fences and risky points, as well as near farms activities

Risk points of interaction between livestock and wildlife

The identification and characterization of potential points of interaction between livestock and wildlife is essential for designing and implementing the specific biosecurity plan at this farm. However, the risk of interspecific contact at each point will depend on the production phase and various temporal factors. Therefore, considering that livestock farming involves two domestic species (pigs and cattle) and that there are three distinct production phases (priming, montanera, and extensive cattle farming), the risk of interaction between them or with wild ungulates, primarily wild boar, varies at each point and phase, and is reflected in Table 8.

Table 8. Points and risk of interspecific interaction in the study farm.

Risk

ID	Guy	Description	Weaning Risk	Montanera Risk	RISK Bovine
X1	POND	<p>Permanent, on XA (see below). Dimensions (m): 43x18 and 76x27 (max.). Fairly clayey, with evidence of wild ungulates in the surrounding mud.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: they do not access, located far from their plots. ▪ Montanera: water availability in XA could reduce its use in this phase, although it is in one of the plots that requires the longest time for use. ▪ Cattle: Possible interaction with pig secretions and excretions if introduced immediately after the montanera. Furthermore, interaction with wild ungulates will be more likely when XA and temporary watering points are dry (summer). 	0	4	5
X2	POND	<p>Temporary, although it usually retains some water almost all summer. Dimensions (m): 6x9 and 24x24 (max.). Located in the most scrubby and densely wooded area east of the path, it shows signs of use by wild ungulates throughout.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: they do not access, located far from their plots. ▪ Montanera: further away from XA. It could be used more than X1 at this stage, both by pigs and wild ungulates, due to its location. ▪ Cattle: Possible interaction with pig secretions and excretions if introduced immediately after the montanera. Furthermore, it is located in the "most favored" area for wild ungulates within this plot. 	0	5	5
X3	POND	<p>Temporary. Dimensions (m): dry at the time of the visit and 17x11 (max.). Located very close to the home (E1). Evidence of use by wild ungulates is not recent.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: they do not access, located far from their plots. ▪ Montanera: only water point on the plot, but it could have limited use due to its small size (short time for use). ▪ Bovine: Possible interaction with porcine secretions and excretions if introduced immediately after the montanera. The remaining interpretation is similar to that indicated for the montanera. 	0	3	4
X4	POND	<p>Permanent. Dimensions (m): 15x12 and 29x18 (max.). Excavated to depth, only part of the surface is easily</p>	0	3	4

		<p>accessible to animals. Few signs of use by wild ungulates.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: they do not access, located far from their plots. ▪ Montanera: could have limited use due to the lower tree density and the small size of the plot (short time for use). ▪ Cattle: Possible interaction with pig secretions and excretions if introduced immediately after the montanera. Furthermore, it is located near the "most favored" area for wild ungulates. 			
X5	POND	<p>Temporary, it only retains water until summer after very rainy springs. Dimensions (m): dry at the time of the visit and 60x58 (max.). Shallow and located in an area largely free of vegetation. Isolated signs of wild ungulates, not recent.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: they do not access, located far from their plots. ▪ Montanera: in addition to the limited time for using the plot (due to its size and tree density), the availability of water in XA and X6 could reduce the use of this point during this phase. ▪ Bovine: Possible interaction with secretions and excretions from pigs if introduced immediately after the montanera. Greater risk of interaction with wild ungulates in late spring, after XA dries, as it would be a wet and muddy surface. 	0	2	3
X6	POND	<p>Permanent, accessible to two plots. Dimensions (m): 34x17 and 57x41 (max.). Fairly clayey, with evidence of use by wild ungulates in the surrounding mud.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: they do not access, located far from their plots. ▪ Montanera: located between the two central plots with the greatest availability of acorns, it is accessible to pigs for longer than the others (X3 - X5). ▪ Bovine: Possible interaction with pig secretions and excretions if introduced immediately after the montanera. Furthermore, it is the only water point accessible from C6 and C7 in summer, when XA and X5 dry up. 	0	4	5
X7	POND	<p>Permanent. Dimensions (m): 14x7 (max.). Excavated deep in very stony ground. Inaccessible to animals.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: may have the effect of attracting wild ungulates to the weaning area in times of scarcity. ▪ Montanera: does not even access the plot. ▪ Cattle: inaccessible. Important: there are no alternative watering points on this plot when XB is dry. 	1	0	0
X8	POND	<p>Permanent. Dimensions (m): 21x6 and 104x18 (max.). Some evidence of use by wild ungulates on the (stony) edges of the pond.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: they do not access, located far from their plots. ▪ Montanera: does not even access the plot. 	0	0	3

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cattle: when they spend more time in this plot (montanera confinement) there is also water available in XB and XC (very close), among other time points. 			
X9	POND	<p>Temporary. Dimensions (m): During the visit, a small wild boar wallow measuring 0.5x0.5m (recently used) and 22x22m (maximum) remained. Located quite far from the wild ungulate refuge area.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: they do not access, located far from their plots. ▪ Montanera: does not even access the plot. ▪ Cattle: when they spend more time in this plot (montanera confinement) there is also water available in XB (very close), among other time points. 	0	0	4
X10	MUDFLAT	<p>Temporary. Dimensions (m): dry at the time of visit and <5x5 (max.). Livestock and wildlife are not usually present.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: Very specific use. ▪ Montanera: does not access. ▪ Bovine: does not access. 	1	0	0
X11	MUDFLAT	<p>Permanent. Dimensions (m): <20x20 (max.). If it dries out, it is artificially filled with water from boreholes or wells (O). Located very close to the facilities. Used by batches of small yearlings. No signs of wild boar are discernible.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: daily use. ▪ Montanera: occasional access, when the acorns in the plot are harvested. Wild ungulates would have to cross various physical barriers to gain access. ▪ Bovine: does not access. 	5	3	0
X12	MUDFLAT	<p>Permanent. Dimensions (m): <20x20 (max.). If it dries out, it is artificially filled with water from boreholes or wells (O). Located very close to the facilities. Used by batches of medium-sized yearlings. No signs of wild boar are discernible.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: daily use. ▪ Montanera: occasional access, when the acorns in the plot are harvested. Wild ungulates would have to cross various physical barriers to gain access. ▪ Bovine: does not access. 	5	3	0
X13	MUDFLAT	<p>Permanent. Dimensions (m): <20x20 (max.). If it dries out, it is artificially filled with water from boreholes or wells (O). Located very close to the facilities. Used by large yearlings. Wild boar signs are indistinguishable.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: daily use. ▪ Montanera: accessible for longer periods of time and with fewer physical barriers for wild ungulates. ▪ Bovine: does not access. 	5	4	0

X14	POND	<p>Permanent. Dimensions (m): 22x14 and 42x29 (max.). Very clayey and located within the grazing area, between two of the grazing plots, it has a livestock fence to prevent access by pigs. However, there are abundant signs of use by wild ungulates, especially wild boar.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: they do not enter unless they manage to cross the fence, but it represents a critical point for the introduction of wild ungulates into their grazing area. ▪ Montanera: they do not enter unless they manage to cross the fence, but it represents a critical point for the introduction of wild ungulates into the grazing area, which is also used in montanera. ▪ Cattle: when they spend more time in this plot (montanera confinement) there is also water available in XB (very close). 	4	3	0
X15	POND	<p>Temporary. Dimensions (m): dry at the time of the visit and 26x14 (max.). Evidence of wild ungulates is not recent.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: they do not access, located far from their plots. ▪ Montanera: excluding XC, it is the only water point available on this plot, although the appearance of other water points as a result of the rain could limit its use in this phase. ▪ Bovine: Possible interaction with pig secretions and excretions if introduced immediately after the montanera. Furthermore, when the area dries out, there are no available water sources (XC dries out much sooner), which can attract wild boar. 	0	4	5
FOR	STREAM	<p>Temporary. Dimensions (m): dry at the time of the visit and <10 (max.). It crosses several farms, but only carries water during the rainy season. There are more water points on the plots it crosses.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: they do not access, located far from their plots. ▪ Montanera: although the flow of water and accessible surface area may dilute the risk of interaction with wild ungulates, the presence of stagnant water can considerably increase it (variable according to rainfall). ▪ Bovine: their permanent presence on the farm increases the chances of contact with wild boar as the water dries up (stagnant waters) as summer progresses. 	0	2 (C6-C7)	3 (C6-C7)
XB	STREAM	<p>Dimensions (m): Dry at the time of the visit and <10 (max.). It flows through several farms, but only carries water during the rainy season. There are more watering points on the plots it crosses, except for C9.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: do not access and are not present when it flows. ▪ Montanera: does not access. ▪ Bovine: it can be the main source of water during the montanera period (C8) or the only one (C9) for the 	0	0	4 (Cacereño in C8)
					5 (Cacereño in C9)
					3 (Aveleño in C10)

		Cacereño, with more water points available for the Avileño (C10).			
XC	STREAM	<p>Dimensions (m): dry at the time of the visit and <5 (max.). Exclusive to the farm and only carries water occasionally during the rainy season.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: do not access, and are not present when it flows. ▪ Montanera: On the one hand, the flow of water and the accessible surface can dilute the risk of interaction with wild boar, and on the other, the slope of the terrain makes it difficult for stagnant water to form. ▪ Bovine: accessible in a small strip very close to both X8 and XB, but with the possibility of generating stagnant waters occasionally. 	0	1	2
B _{E3}	DRINKING FOUNTAINS IN COURTYARDS	<p>Various pig waterers are located at the E3 facilities, in the concrete yards isolated from the outdoor plots. Water comes from boreholes or, alternatively, from wells (O) and is only available during feeding time in the yards.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: daily use. ▪ Montanera: does not access. ▪ Bovine: does not access. 	1	0	0
Bp	DRINKING FOUNTAINS PLOTS	<p>Various pig waterers located on plots C11-C13. Commercial type with a cemented base (see appendix). Water comes from boreholes or, alternatively, from wells (O), and is always available.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: daily use. More accessible to wild boar than the previous ones. If there are leaks, small pools form around them. ▪ Montanera: occasional access, when the acorns in the plot are harvested. Wild ungulates would have to cross various physical barriers to gain access. ▪ Bovine: does not access. 	3	2	0
Bb	BOVINE DRINKING TROUGHS	<p>Two cattle drinking troughs are located in plots C8 (metal and elevated; see appendix) and C14 (tub type). Water comes from a borehole or, alternatively, from wells (O), and is always available (C8) or used when cattle are being handled (C14).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: they do not enter, but their location could favor direct contact through the fence. ▪ Montanera: does not access. ▪ Bovine: they are low in height and can become flooded if there are overflows. 	1	0	2
O	WELLS	Various groundwater extraction points for domestic use (boreholes) and livestock use (boreholes and wells if there are any borehole failures). The periphery is	1	1	1

		<p>inaccessible to animals, as they are well insulated and waterproofed.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: could be a source of infection carried by drinking water in drinking troughs and mudholes. ▪ Montanera: they do not access borehole/well water (except in the mudflats). ▪ Bovine: they could be a source of infection carried by drinking water in drinking troughs. 			
E2	BUILDINGS	<p>Structures for future building construction. Use for concrete feeding/roosting of pigs during free-range pig farming (E2a and E2b; E2c is no longer in use).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: they do not access, located far from their area. ▪ Montanera: use of concrete feeding pens, especially at the beginning of this phase, to facilitate the animals' adaptation to the new plots. Risk of attracting wild ungulates to the feed. ▪ Cattle: No access during montanera (confinement). Use for this species unknown. 	0	3	??
E3	WEANING CENTER	<p>Feeding and handling facility for the young animals, equipped with concrete yards isolated from the outside plots. Feed is stored in silos.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weaning: risk of attracting wild boars due to the existence (smell) of resources, mainly food, although it is inaccessible to them. ▪ Montanera: no access, and there are no yearlings in the center at this stage. ▪ Bovine: does not access. 	1	0	0

Proposed biosecurity measures in livestock farming

General measures refer to interventions that affect the comprehensive management of livestock, wildlife, or resources. **Specific measures**, on the other hand, They refer to the specific actions that should be taken at points where a risk of interaction between livestock species and between these and wildlife has been identified; they are detailed in Table 9.

GENERAL BIOSECURITY MEASURES

❖ Health management and control of livestock movements

The National TB Eradication Program must be strictly adhered to, as without this initial requirement, all action would be secondary. Furthermore, in the absence of a specific campaign to combat this disease in pigs, any movement of animals of unknown health status carries an additional risk. Therefore, a negative serological diagnosis for TB is recommended for all pigs entering and leaving the farm. However, the unprecedented emergence of TB in cattle could be associated not only with domestic reservoirs but also with interaction with wild reservoirs in the farm.

❖ Game management

Hunting pressure on wild ungulates can have a direct impact on their populations and, consequently, on their land use. Given that almost all the surrounding farms are used for agricultural and livestock farming, a shared interest in reducing the populations of these species must be considered, for example, by coordinating game management plans. The implementation of different methods of big game hunting, such as hunting hunts or different types of drives, can contribute to this objective at the farm, especially if these practices are maintained over time. It is essential not to provide supplementary feed for wild game (feeding areas) to avoid the potential attraction effect of these species, which would be counterproductive to livestock farming interests. Furthermore, it is recommended not to graze plot C10 while it is being fattened for small game.

❖ Management of enclosures and fences on plots

The implementation of a perimeter hunting fence could reduce the frequency of wild ungulate entry from neighboring farms, where they appear to have their main refuge area. The current capacity of livestock fences to contain wildlife is very limited, even in the grazing plots, where they are theoretically in better condition (in fact, we identified a wild boar grazing area in these plots during the visit). Due to this permeability, the risk of interaction with livestock is similar and very high in all plots. To minimize the chances of infection through this route, it is recommended to waterproof, with hunting fencing, at least the grazing area (plots C11-C15), especially considering that nearly 1,400 pigs are generated each year, to be distributed for montanera not only on this farm but also on other farms. Furthermore, it would be advisable to reduce the size of these plots to spatially segregate the grazing of yearlings and the montanera. On the other hand, and although it does not contribute to significantly reducing the frequency of wildlife entry, regular inspections of the remaining internal fences are important to ensure their effectiveness in containing livestock and preventing pig-cow contact during the montanera period.

❖ Water point management

Three types of watering points accessible to both livestock (cattle and pigs) and wildlife (wild boar, deer, and badgers) have been identified on the farm: ponds/ mud pits, streams, and drinking troughs. The use of each depends primarily on characteristics, such as height or surrounding fencing, that facilitate or impede access for different species. In general, it is recommended to segregate the use of watering points by pigs, cattle, and wild ungulates, providing specific points for each of these species.

Pools should be avoided as direct access points to water for livestock, by eliminating or fencing them off, and replaced by selective drinking troughs (see appendix), ideally supplied with water from a well or borehole, or if this is not possible, from the pools themselves, fenced. Pool X14 should be removed, as it is not used for livestock farming and can be an important attraction point for wild ungulates, particularly wild boar. Streams, which have water seasonally, pose risk points for interaction that vary over time. It is recommended, as far as possible, to avoid access by livestock to excessively muddy stagnant water areas, especially for cattle in summer.

Drinking trough management is divided into three main actions: hygiene, installation of new units, and conditioning or repair of existing ones. It is essential to maintain them in hygienic conditions and disinfect them frequently. The configuration of the drinkers appears adequate, especially the commercial ones, although it is recommended to provide a higher elevation for the CATTLE drinkers and to improve the PIG drinkers with a cover system to facilitate selective use by each species (see appendix). A selective watering point must be installed in plot C17, where cattle and pigs cannot drink. Furthermore, it is recommended to install selective watering points in plots where puddles are eliminated and there are no other alternatives (no drinking troughs or streams with seasonal flow). In any case, the water should not overflow from the drinkers, as this would form small, muddy pools around them, which could represent a critical risk point for interspecific aggregation. To avoid this situation, it is recommended to regulate the water flow and pressure, the buoy system, and, additionally, install a cemented base in drinking fountains that do not have one, protruding approximately 1 m on each side.

❖ *Pasture management*

At the farm, rotational management of plots is carried out to maximize the use of resources. In this context, where the circulation of pathogens between domestic and wild animals can be favored, the segregation of different species is essential. Avoiding the shared use of Charolais stallions could contribute to minimizing direct transmission between Cácereno and Avileño cattle. Furthermore, the implementation of empty periods (without livestock) at the spatial and temporal level in the plots, that is, avoiding the presence of two livestock species in adjacent plots and preventing one species from grazing in plots previously used by another (leaving an interval of at least one month), can be useful, together with the previous recommendations regarding fencing and watering points, to reduce indirect transmission.

❖ *Management of carrion and livestock by-products*

This farm has an adequate management system for bovine carrion and by-products, consisting of an official removal service. Pork carcasses are made available to scavengers at a cleared area located on the neighboring farm. Any carcasses or game carcasses that may be generated on the farm are deposited at this same area. Since the disposal site does not have additional physical barriers (fences) that limit access to opportunistic scavenging mammals (such as wild boar), it is recommended that these carcasses and by-products be deposited early in the morning to encourage their consumption by scavengers. Once the by-products have been consumed, the remaining waste is collected and buried or incinerated

on the farm. Considering that this point does not constitute a true authorized dump, it is recommended to request the corresponding authorization to enable it as such.

SPECIFIC BIOSECURITY MEASURES

Table 9. Specific biosecurity measures at points of risk of interspecific interaction.

ID	Description	Specific Recommended Actions
FENCE C11-C15	WEANING PLOTS used by pigs in the primary phase and also accessible in MONTANERA	<p>OPTION 1</p> <p>Reduce the grazing area for medium and large yearlings (avoiding use of plot C12B and drawing a line that continues from the boundary between C12A and B to C16). Replace livestock fencing with game fencing throughout the entire grazing area to prevent access by wild ungulates (wild boar and deer).</p> <p><i>Note:</i> This measure assumes complete segregation of yearlings from montanera cattle. If cattle (C14-C15) are being managed, do not introduce yearlings for at least one month.</p>
		<p>OPTION 2</p> <p>Reduce the grazing area for medium and large yearlings (avoiding using plot C12B and drawing a line that continues from the boundary between C12A and B to C16). Reinforce the livestock fence in the lower part of the grazing area or install an electric fence to make it more impervious to wild boar.</p> <p><i>Note:</i> like option 1, this measure does not reduce the risk of deer entering the plots.</p>
X1, X2, X3, X4, X5, X6, X15	Ponds inaccessible to yearlings and used by pigs during the montanera period and by cattle the rest of the year.	<p>OPTION 1</p> <p>Peripheral fencing to prevent access to livestock and replacement of the watering point with selective drinking troughs for each species.</p> <p><i>Note:</i> This measure would minimize interaction with wild ungulates in the ponds. <u>PRIORITY: X2, X15, X1 and X6.</u></p>
		<p>OPTION 2</p> <p>Peripheral fencing with an access gate or temporary electric fence to prevent access to cattle, but not to pigs, and installation of elevated drinking troughs for cattle.</p> <p><i>Note:</i> This measure would minimize the interaction of cattle with wild ungulates, but not between these and pigs in montanera.</p>
X8, X9	Exclusive ponds for cattle.	<p>OPTION 1</p> <p>Peripheral fencing to prevent access to cattle, and installation of elevated drinking troughs inaccessible to wild boar.</p>
X14	POND located between two grazing plots for yearlings (C12-C13) but inaccessible to pigs,	<p>OPTION 1</p> <p>Complete removal of this water point (burying it) and the fence that delimits plot C12B with C13 to build a single montanera plot (new creation), and installation of a selective drinking trough (with lids) towards the center of the plot.</p>

	with abundant evidence of use by wild boar.	<p><i>Note:</i> This measure could minimize the attraction effect of wild boar to these plots and, therefore, to the rounding area.</p> <p>OPTION 2</p> <p>Elimination of the pond and replacement with selective drinking troughs for each of the two new montanera plots.</p> <p><i>Note:</i> this measure could minimize the effect of attracting wild boar to the area of rounding, but to a lesser extent than option 1, since the preference for this species is not eliminated by point X14.</p>
X11, X12, X13	Wharves or small ponds in the outer plots designated for the various batches of yearlings, also currently accessible for montanera.	<p>OPTION 1</p> <p>Peripheral fencing to prevent access to pigs or elimination of these watering points, and increasing the number of low drinking troughs in each plot.</p> <p><i>Note:</i> This measure would promote the ingestion of water of better hygienic-sanitary quality, making it difficult for any mycobacteria present in the mud to persist in the environment.</p>
		<p>OPTION 2</p> <p>Peripheral fence with access gate.</p> <p><i>Note:</i> This measure would make this resource available to the yearlings when the rancher deems it appropriate. This is especially important during the hottest days of the summer.</p>
FOR	Temporary stream that runs through the eastern part of the farm (north to south). Accessible to free-range pigs and Cacereño cattle.	<p>OPTION 1</p> <p>Prevent access to muddy surfaces and stagnant water by using electric fences or temporary fencing.</p>
		<p>OPTION 2</p> <p>Implement permanent livestock fences, subdividing the plots, to prevent access to these areas.</p> <p><i>Note:</i> This measure would involve the installation of a greater number of drinking fountains on newly created plots that lose access to existing water points, unless the new drinking fountains are accessible from two adjacent plots.</p>
XB	Temporary stream that runs through the farm through the central or secluded plots (north to south). Accessible to cattle.	<p>OPTION 1</p> <p>Implement permanent livestock fencing on both sides of the stream at C8 and C9 to prevent access to Cacereño cattle (where the TB outbreak occurred) by dividing each plot in two and installing three additional elevated water troughs, one in each new subplot without a watering point. Prevent Avileño cattle from accessing muddy surfaces and stagnant water at C10 using electric fences or temporary fencing.</p>
		<p>OPTION 2</p> <p>Avoid grazing the fields it crosses when the water stops flowing and muddy surfaces form, for at least one month.</p> <p><i>Note:</i> This measure depends on weather conditions. This period may also overlap with the montanera period. It is essential to respect the post-montanera period of emptying in the plots.</p>

Bp	DRINKING FOUNTAINS FOR COMMERCIAL PLOTS.	OPTION 1 Improve with a selective capping system. Repair existing leaks to prevent peripheral flooding. Implement a periodic cleaning and disinfection protocol.
Bb	Commercial BOVINE DRINKING TROLLEYS-BATHTUB.	OPTION 1 Replace bathtub with commercial drinking fountain. Raise height. Cement base. Maintain regular cleaning and disinfection protocol.
E2	BUILDINGS used for feeding and roosting during montanera.	OPTION 1 Implement a permanent livestock fence around the structure, leaving access for livestock, and reinforce the lower section to prevent wild boar from accessing the "temporary feeding yard."

In summary, the main general situations and specific points of risk of interaction between domestic and wild species, on which it is recommended to implement biosecurity measures would be, in each of the productive phases present in the farm:

WEANING PIGS

Certification of health status (at source), spatial segregation of pigs during free-range grazing (reducing the grazing area during round-up grazing), and waterproofing the entire production area to protect against wild ungulates (wild boar and deer). In this regard, it is essential to correct the situation at pond X14, as well as implement specific measures at watering points (swamps > drinking troughs).

MONTANERA

In addition to the recommendations for the weaning phase (pigs in montanera are raised on the farm itself), proper management of pastures and fences is essential to avoid contact (direct and indirect) with cattle and wild ungulates. Various game management measures aimed at reducing or controlling populations could minimize potential contact with wild boar or deer. An abundance of natural water (rainfall and torrential water) reduces the risk of interaction at permanent watering points during this phase.

BOVINE

It is essential to comply with the National Tuberculosis Eradication Program by introducing only animals that are negative for official diagnostic techniques, both stallions and Avilenian cattle temporarily present. By confining this species to the farm's central plots during the montanera period, the main risk of interaction with pigs or wild ungulates is at watering points (ponds > stagnant water in streams).

4. Conclusions

- » This farm is a highly professional, extensive livestock farm that aims to minimize the risk of disease transmission, especially TB, from wildlife and domestic reservoirs present on the farm.
- » The main source of risk from wildlife is wild boar, which is identified on farms more frequently than deer. It is recommended to increase wild boar removal rates in the region (both within the hunting area and neighboring reserves), for example, by coordinating game management plans, increasing the number of hunts, or incorporating other hunting methods, such as waiting, in areas with a high livestock density where hunting can be excessively complex.
- » The incorporation of livestock from outside the farm must be carried out under the best possible sanitary conditions. A TB diagnosis of incoming and outgoing animals is necessary (mandatory for cattle and highly recommended for pigs) to minimize the potential risk of infection via this route, both on the farm itself and on the receiving farms. Furthermore, it is recommended to assess the TB status of wild ungulates from hunting activities in the region to monitor the circulation of mycobacteria.
- » The appearance, for the first time, of cattle testing positive for TB using official diagnostic techniques in 2018, as well as the detection of seropositive pigs after the montanera phase in the last campaign (2017-2018), highlight the need to implement biosecurity measures to mitigate interspecific contact and reduce the risk of transmission of diseases such as TB between these species. To quantify the degree of interaction and analyze its impact on TB epidemiology, various risk points will be monitored using camera trapping techniques.
- » The main interventions would include smart management of plots, pastures, and fences to achieve effective species segregation in both space and time; reinforcing the fencing of the breeding area; specific interventions at watering points; and installing additional species-specific drinking fountains.
- » The implementation of the proposed measures must be effective in reducing the risk of TB outbreaks in the future, as well as other infectious diseases. However, we insist on the need to continue implementing biosecurity measures to minimize the risk of infection in this farm.

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Contact

SaBio - IREC (UCLM)

7. Annexes

Sheet of actions implemented in the farm.

This sheet, once completed after the implementation of biosecurity measures, must be sent to:

National Institute on Wildlife Research (IREC)			
Mail: xxxxxx, Telephone: nnnnnn			
Proposed General Actions		Done Yes/No	Observations/Modifications Investment made (€)
Health management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Incorporation and exit of TB-negative cattle (official control). ▪ Incorporation and removal of TB-negative pigs (ELISA). ▪ TB monitoring in wild ungulates of game origin in the region (ELISA). 		
Game management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Carrying out wild boar waits within the farm. ▪ Carrying out additional raids within the farm. ▪ Coordination of hunting management plans among neighbors. 		
Fence management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Regular review of maintenance status. ▪ Cover the passages opened by wild boar. ▪ Implementation of a perimeter hunting fence. 		
Pasture management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Avoid sharing Charolais stallions between Cáceres and Avila cows. ▪ Maintain a one-month vacuum period between cattle and pigs before and after the montanera. ▪ Maintain an empty plot (without livestock) between two plots grazed by different species. 		
By-product and carrion management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Deposit them early in the morning to ensure they are eliminated by necrophagous birds. ▪ Request authorization for a private dump for pork and game by-products. ▪ Implement an official withdrawal service for porcine species. 		
Proposed Specific Actions		Done Yes/No	Observations/Modifications Investment made (€)
FENCES C11-C15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>OPTION 1</u>: Implement a hunting fence from the C12A-B divide to C16 and replace the perimeter livestock fence of the rounding-up area with a hunting fence. ▪ <u>OPTION 2</u>: Implement the same fencing, but for livestock, and reinforce the perimeter fencing of the rounding-up area at the bottom or incorporate an electric fence (including the new one). 		
X1, X2, X3, X4, X5, X6, X15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>OPTION 1</u>: Peripheral fencing to prevent access to domestic animals and replacement of the water 		

(MONTANERA PONDS-CATTLE)	point with selective drinking fountains for each species (see appendix).		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>OPTION 2:</u> Peripheral fencing with an access gate or temporary electric fence to prevent access to cattle but not pigs, and installation of elevated drinking troughs for cattle. 		
X8, X9 (BOVINE PONDS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>OPTION 1:</u> Peripheral fencing to prevent access to cattle, and installation of elevated drinking troughs inaccessible to wild boar. 		
X14 (WILD BOAR POND)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>OPTION 1:</u> Complete removal of this water point (burial) and the fence dividing C12B with C13, and installation of a better located selective drinking fountain. 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>OPTION 2:</u> Elimination of the pond and replacement with selective drinking troughs for each of the montanera subplots. 		
X11, X12, X13 (WEANING MUDFLAT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>OPTION 1:</u> Peripheral fencing to prevent access to the yearlings or elimination of these water points and increasing the number of low drinking troughs in each plot. 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>OPTION 2:</u> Peripheral fencing with temporary access gate. 		
FOR EAST STREAM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>OPTION 1:</u> Prevent access to stagnant water by using temporary electric fences. 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>OPTION 2:</u> Implement permanent livestock fences by subdividing the plots to avoid grazing plots with stagnant water. 		
XB (CENTER STREAM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>OPTION 1:</u> Implement permanent livestock fencing on both sides of the stream at C8 and C9 to prevent access to Cacereño cattle (where the TB outbreak occurred), dividing each plot in two and installing three additional elevated water troughs, one in each new subplot without a watering point. Prevent Avileño cattle from accessing muddy surfaces and stagnant water at C10 using electric fences or temporary fencing. 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>OPTION 2:</u> Avoid grazing the plots it crosses when the water stops flowing and muddy surfaces and stagnant water form, for at least one month. 		
B p (WEANING PLOT DRINKING FOUNTAINS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>OPTION 1:</u> Improve with a selective lid system (see appendix). Repair existing leaks to prevent peripheral flooding. Implement a periodic cleaning and disinfection protocol. 		
Bb (CATTLE DRINKING TROUGHS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>OPTION 1:</u> Replace bathtub with commercial drinking fountain. Raise height. Cement base. 		

	Maintain regular cleaning and disinfection protocol.		
E2 (MONTANERA BUILDINGS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>OPTION 1</u>: Implement a permanent livestock fence around the structure, leaving access for livestock, and reinforce the lower section to prevent wild boar from accessing the "temporary feeding yard." 		

Photographic annex

Low risk

Figure 5. Limited possibility of interaction between domestic and wildlife. (A) Disused well, (B) E2 type structure, (C) Feeding yard within the E3 weaning center, (D) X7 pond.

Moderate risk

Figure 6. (A) Pond X5, (B) Pond X6, (C) Internal livestock fence.

High risk

Figure 7. (A) Pond X1, (B) Pond X14. Recent indications of use by wild boar in plots where no other domestic species existed at the time of the visit are detailed.

Risk situations

Figure 8. Charolais stallion in proximity to the C11 fence (top), and wild boar juvenile next to the batch of C13 weaning (bottom), highlighting potential direct (bottom) and indirect (top and bottom) interspecific contacts.

Improvement of commercial type drinking trough for cattle

Figure 9. Bb drinking trough in plot C8 (left), and example of a drinking trough of the same type but raised to prevent access to the suids (right). It would be advisable to cement the base.

Improved selective pig drinker with cemented lid and base

Figure 10. Bp drinking trough of plot C13, where a leak or failure in the buoy system (above) is evident, and model of selective drinking trough for pigs with a lid system and cemented base. Pilot experience carried out by IREC. Improvement of selective drinking trough for pigs with lid and cemented base.

Annex 6

Farm- Specific external biosecurity plan with special attention to African swine fever risks

Example 2 Intensive pig production

SABIO
Sanidad y Biotecnología
Health and Biotechnology

World Organisation
for Animal Health

This real example has been developed by Health and Biotechnology Group of the National Institute on Wildlife Research (IREC) of the University of Castile-La Mancha/CSIC/JCCM.

Index

BIOSECURITY RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The importance of biosecurity to prevent the spread of African Swine Fever in domestic pigs

African Swine Fever Virus

Current epidemiological situation

Routes of infection and environmental persistence of African Swine Fever virus

2. Biosecurity in pig farms

Biosecurity programs: a complementary tool

Regulations related to biosecurity in pigs

Work methodology

3. Description of the livestock farm

General characteristics and design of the farm

Biosecurity characteristics

4. Identification of risks and proposed biosecurity measures

Perimeter fencing of the farm and facilities

Farm environment

Introduction of the animals

Vehicle management and animal transport

Personnel management

Other

5. Conclusions

6. Bibliographic references

7. Annex

Cleaning and disinfection protocol

Photo archive

1. African Swine Fever in pigs

African Swine Fever Virus

The African Swine Fever (ASF) is an infectious disease caused by a virus of the family *Asfarviridae*, genus *Asfivirus*, which affects domestic and several species of wild suids, but not humans. In general, The infection progresses acutely, with nonspecific symptoms such as fever, hemorrhagic skin lesions, and cyanosis, usually localized to the ears, limbs, tail, and snout. The lesions found in affected animals include splenomegaly (the spleen also acquires a purplish color), edema, and hemorrhages in most of the serosa of the internal organs.

Currently, ASF is the subject of surveillance and eradication in industrialized countries due to his implication in Health Animal, Health Public and in the management and conservation of wild suid species.

Current epidemiological situation

In Europe, pigs are the main domestic reservoir of the disease, and wild boars are the main wild reservoir. In areas of Africa where the disease is endemic, it also affects wild suids, in which no symptoms are observed. It can also fatally affect other wild suid species, such as in Southeastern Asia.

Since entering Eastern Europe in 2007, the disease has inexorably spread westward. It entered the European Union in 2014, and since then, cases have been reported in both wild boar and domestic pigs, although in the latter, it has been mainly linked to farms with poor biosecurity and backyard measures. Currently, this pathogen is present in wild boar and domestic pigs in 12 European Union countries: Bulgaria, the Czech Republic, Estonia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, and the Czech Republic. The disease was detected in wild boar in Belgium in 2018 but was eradicated in 2020.

Routes of infection and environmental persistence of the African swine fever virus

The main route of entry of this virus into the body is oronasal, and as a systemic disease, it affects different organs. This is why the excretion routes are multiple: two days after infection, the virus is already present in saliva and ocular and nasal secretions. The virus is subsequently excreted in urine, feces, and semen.

The main modes of transmission among swine are through direct contact between animals or with the carcasses of infected animals. However, due to its high persistence in pork products or contaminated materials (e.g., vehicles, clothing, or footwear), this virus can travel long distances and appear far from affected areas. Outbreaks associated with the transport and exchange of infected animals have also been described. Other described modes of transmission include manure, contaminated feed or pasture, surgical equipment and/or medical examinations, and ticks of the genus *Ornithodoros*, although the role of the latter is currently considered minor in the epidemiology of the disease in Europe.

2. Biosecurity in farms livestock

Programs of biosecurity: a tool complementary

Biosecurity is defined as the set of physical measures (e.g., perimeter fencing, aviary netting, etc.) and management measures (e.g., carcass management, grazing management, etc.) taken to prevent the entry (external biosecurity) and spread (internal biosecurity) of a pathogen on a farm. However, due to the unique situation of each farm, risks must be specifically assessed and a biosecurity program designed to be effective, practical, and feasible.

In the swine sector, these types of programs are essential for preventing and controlling ASF and other infectious diseases, including Aujeszky's disease, hepatitis E, porcine brucellosis, trichinosis, and porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome (PRRS).

Regulations related with biosecurity in cattle porcine

- » Regulation (EU) 1375/2015, establishing specific rules for official controls of the presence of trichinae in meat.
- » Regulation (EU) No 217/2014, relating to Salmonella in pig carcasses.
- » Regulation (EC) No. 852/2004, relating to the hygiene of foodstuffs.
- » Regulation (EU) No. 218/2014, that modifies the annexes of the Regulations 853/2004 and 854/2004.
- » Regulation (EU) 2016/429 on transmissible animal diseases and amending or repealing certain acts relating to animal health ('Animal Health Law').

Methodology of biosecurity assessment in pig intensive farms

The OBJECTIVE of this real case is to provide technical advice on external biosecurity for the mitigation of risk with special emphasis on wildlife and ASF in intensive pig farms

The phases into this work is divided are:

- i) **Description of the pig farm:** general data and mapping.
- ii) **Visit *in situ*:** epidemiological survey and identification of risk points.
- iii) **Quantification of the farm's risk level:** including a comparison of the risk level with farms of the same zootechnical classification and in the same area.
- iv) **Specific recommendations on biosecurity:** they are specific to this example farm.

3. Description of the pig management

General characteristics and design of the farm

Table 1. General data of the exploitation

Name of the farm	XXXXX
Municipality	xxxx
Total census	Sows: 3300 Replacement: 274 Boars: 2
Zootechnical classification of the farm	Piglet production
All-in/All-out system	In maternity: no In adaptation/quarantine: yes
Other domestic animals on the farm	None
Diseases diagnosed in recent years	Piglet diarrhea caused by rotavirus E. coli, clostridiosis, APP

Characteristics of biosecurity

Table 2. Epidemiological survey

Location of the farm	Distance to four nearest intensive pig farms	- 4,500 meters: about 2,000 fattening pigs - 4,500 meters: about 2,000 fattening pigs - 4,500 meters: about 2,000 fattening pigs
	Distance to four nearest extensive pig farms	- 400 meters: less than 1000 sheep
	Distance to nearest landfill	More than 10,000 meters
	Distance to nearest slaughterhouse	More than 10,000 meters
	Distance to the nearest type I and II by-product treatment plant	More than 10,000 meters
	Distance to nearest type III by-product treatment plant	More than 10,000 meters
	Distance to nearest public road	2,000 meters
	Distance to big game hunting reserve	0 meters
Perimeter fencing	Fence or barrier that physically separates the perimeter of the property from the outside	Yes
	Type of fence or barrier (there may be several)	2.3 meter simple torsion mesh anchored to concrete, with tall vegetation at the base Folding fence with concrete base, total height 2m
	Percentage of fenced perimeter	100
	Frequency of review of the perimeter fence	Monthly
	Existence of wild boar passages in the perimeter	No

	fence	
	Farm exteriors in good condition of cleanliness and maintenance	No
	Accesses always closed	Yes
	Waterproof access to wild boar	No
Fencing of the facilities	Specific fencing of some facilities	Yes, there is an interior fence surrounding the buildings.
	Type of fencing	2-meter simple torsion mesh on unanchored concrete or soil, with tall vegetation at the base
	Frequency of fence inspection	Monthly
	Existence of wild boar passages in the fence	No
	Accesses always closed	Yes
	Waterproof access to wild boar	Yes
	Existence of camping	No
Characterization of the operating environment	Crops in the surroundings of the farm	Almond, cereal, fruit trees, adjacent to the farm
	Forest areas in the vicinity of the farm	Riparian forest at 1,500 meters
	Water points in the surroundings of the farm	Pond at 450 meters, 125 meters in diameter, unfenced, 20% accessible to wildlife (wild boar tracks were found nearby) River at 1,500 meters
	Evidence of the presence of wild boar in the surroundings of the farm	Yes, a wild boar bath was found near the west fence and tracks bordering the perimeter in that area.
Characterization of the interior of the farm	Crops grown inside the farm	No
	Forest areas within the farm	No
	Water points inside the farm	No

Game Management/Wildlife	Livestock farming within a hunting area	Yes
	Number of wild boars hunted/season	19
	Number of deer hunted/season	4
	Number of roe deer hunted/season	10
	Percentage of limiting perimeter with big game hunting reserve	100%
	Frequency of sightings of common fauna species	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wild boar: very sporadic - Deer: very sporadic - Roe deer: very sporadic - Badger: very sporadic - Fox: monthly
	Areas where wildlife is most frequently observed	Small patch of scrubland to the southeast and a large patch to the southwest; cornfields, the furthest area about 250 meters away
	Season when more wild boars are detected in the	Summer and autumn

	surroundings of the farm	
	Season when more wild boars are detected inside the farm	A wild boar has never been seen on the farm
	Increased presence of wild boar associated with the heat of females	No
Entrance of the animals	Origins of animals	2-3 origins
	Loading the animals	Charge separately
	Number of annual entries	More than 5 entries
Vehicles	Vehicles enter the farm	No (since they do not pass the fence of the warehouses, it is considered that they do not penetrate the perimeter)
	Vehicles leave the farm	No
	Loading dock within the facilities	No
	Approach of the carcass collecting vehicle	Perimeter area of the property
	Access of the carcass collection vehicle by the same road as others	Yes
	Access of the slurry vehicle by the same road as others	Yes
	Existence of a ford/disinfection arch	Yes
	Frequency of inspection of the ford/arch	Weekly
Management of carcasses	Accessibility to carcasses by scavengers	Never
	Carcass disposal system (adults and piglets)	100% official withdrawal, with hydrolysis
	Temporality in mortality	12.3 cases/week on average, concentrated mainly from May to October
Slurry management	Slurry tank outside the perimeter	Yes
	Slurry management plan	Yes
	Accessibility of wild boars to the slurry pond	No
	Type of fencing for the slurry pond	1.8 meter high unburied single torsion mesh with tall vegetation at the base and cat flaps
Water	Water tank outside the perimeter	Yes
	Disinfected drinking water	Yes, with chlorine dioxide. It also has a fiberglass filter.
	Accessibility of wild boars to the water source	No
Food	Consumption of recently harvested food	No
	Leaks in silos	No

	Registration of feed suppliers/deliveries	Yes
	Type of food by production phase	Compound feed in all phases
Staff	Consumption of pork products on the farm by staff	Yes (in the designated dining room)
	Employees are shared with other farms	No
	Employees with close contact with hunting activities	No
	Clean locker room	Yes
	Separation of clean/dirty areas in the locker room	Yes
	Existence of footbaths/shoe shiners at the entrance to the farm	Yes
	Exclusive clothing for workers	Yes
	Visitors' logbook	Yes
	Exclusive clothing for visitors	Yes
	Quarantine facility material exclusive to this	Yes
	Staff	Posters with instructions on hygiene measures
Hygiene and biosafety training plans		Yes
Cleaning, disinfection, rat extermination and disinfestation	LDDD Records	Yes
	LDDD program monitoring systems	Yes
	Performed by specific personnel for LDDD	No
	Authorized personnel for LDDD	Yes
	Bird nets	Yes
	Rodent control systems	Yes
	Mosquito nets	No
	Strict pest control program	Yes, occasionally carried out by an external company
	Specific control/control program for <i>Ornithodoros moubata</i>	No
Questions answered by the farmer	Five most important biosecurity measures to prevent the entry of diseases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fencing of the facilities - Vehicle access control - Management of corpses - Certified origin of feed - Certified origin of semen
	Compliance with biosecurity measures	9
	Additional comments	Goods entering the farm are disinfected with ozone. A leak was detected in a cooler in the maternity ward.

4. Quantifying the level of risk

Risk quantification is achieved by assigning a score based on the risk it represents: 0 for low risk, 0.5 for medium risk, and 1 for high risk. This gives to the score assigned by observers to each block (different dimensions for which specific risk can be grouped). A panel of 16 experts from different public and private entities was then asked about the importance of each block based on the risk it poses to the introduction of ASF into a farm (either through wildlife or products or materials contaminated by it). These experts assigned a score to each block, which (the average value) is multiplied by the risk level assigned by observers visiting *in situ* this farm to obtain the total risk for each block. Finally, the risk for each block is added together to obtain the farm's total risk level. These calculations are summarized in the following table:

After calculating the risk level, it was found that this farm has good biosecurity. Its risk level (see below) is on the average of other farms in the same area, both in maternity and fattening wards, and even lower than maternity wards in other areas.

5. I identification of risks and proposed measures of biosecurity

Perimeter fencing of the farm and facilities

RISKS:

- ☒ Monthly fence review: to detect new underpasses, especially after torrential rains. In this regard, it has been observed that underpasses could soon appear in the southern sector fence due to runoff.
- ☒ Tall vegetation at the base of the exterior and interior fence: risk of using this area as a refuge for wildlife, especially rodents.
- ☒ Access to the perimeter fence permeable to wild boar at the gate adjacent to the slurry pond: possibility of access of species sympatric (rodents, foxes, badgers and even small wild boars, among others).
- ☒ Interior fence not anchored to the ground: risk of wildlife lifting it and gaining access to the interior of the farm.

PROPOSED MEASURES:

- ✓ **Increase the frequency of fence checks**: A weekly check of the fence allows you to quickly identify any potential openings and repair the fence before wildlife can enter the farm.
- ✓ **Remove vegetation at the base of the fence**: either by mechanical or chemical means.
- ✓ **Waterproof the lower area of the permeable access**: to make the perimeter fence fully effective, for example, by installing a wire mesh, creating a concrete ramp under the gate, or replacing the gate with one that fits snugly against the ground.
- ✓ **Installation of an interior fence impermeable to wildlife**: either by anchoring it to the concrete base (in some places this fence is on a concrete surface but not attached to it) or by burying it 30 cm into the ground.

Farm surroundings

RISKS:

- ☒ Signs of wild boar in the surroundings of the farm: a wild boar bath was found near the parking lot and footprints bordering the perimeter fence on the southwest corner.
- ☒ Pond near the farm: It is 450 meters from the farm, is not fenced and around 20% of the perimeter is accessible to wildlife, so it can be a focal point for wildlife.

PROPOSED MEASURES:

- ✓ **Cover the area where the evidence was found with a concrete slab**: the goal is to prevent water from accumulating in that area and attract wildlife.
- ✓ **Installing a waterproof wildlife fence around the pond**: This could be limited to the area accessible to wildlife. It should be anchored to a concrete base or buried 30 centimeters deep.
- ✓ **It is recommended to increase hunting pressure on wild boar to reduce the risk of this species' presence in the vicinity of the farm.**

Animal movements

RISKS:

- ☒ Animals from two or three sources and more than five movements (entries) per year: The number of animals from different sources entering the farm poses a high risk of pathogen entry. Cases of ASF have been reported in association with the transport of infected animals.

PROPOSED MEASURES:

- ✓ **Safe origin of replacement animals**: always bring in animals from safe sources, certified as having good health status. Avoid, as far as possible, importing pigs from countries affected by ASF.

- ✓ **Conducting diagnostic tests upon entry and exit from quarantine:** this way, we can ensure that animals enter the facility free of pathogens and do not infect others.

Vehicle management and animal transport

RISKS:

- ☒ **Access for carcass and slurry vehicles via the same road as the rest of the vehicles:** all vehicles arrive at the farm via the same access road. Even if neither of them enters the farm, they can carry pathogens from other farms into the surrounding area and/or contaminate other vehicles.

PROPOSED MEASURES:

- ✓ **Continue to maintain strict separation between the clean and dirty areas of the farm:** prevent outside vehicles from entering the inner fence and prevent staff from leaving the farm wearing clothing outside the fence. Maintaining footbaths at the farm entrance in good condition helps maintain this separation.
- ✓ **Disinfection of these vehicles at the entrance to the farm's access road:** a less expensive option could be using a backpack sprayer, both at the entrance and exit of these vehicles.
- ✓ **Use of an alternative access route:** for example, the track leading into the farm from the east could be opened.

Staff

RISKS:

- ☒ Consumption of pork products on farm: Contaminated meat products are one of the main transmission routes for this disease. Even if they are consumed exclusively in the dining room, their introduction into the farm poses a risk.

PROPOSED MEASURES:

- ✓ **Prohibit the introduction and consumption of these products on the farm**: This simple measure eliminates a significant risk of the virus entering the farm.

Others

RISKS:

- ☒ Leak in a cooler in the maternity ward: This leak creates a puddle that can be a draw for wildlife, especially during dry seasons, when this resource is scarce in the natural environment.

PROPOSED MEASURES:

- ✓ **Check the cooling system and repair the leak**: this will eliminate this attraction for wildlife.

6. Conclusions

- » This is a piglet production farm that demonstrated good biosecurity. Good practices related to internal biosecurity are notable, with some specific deficiencies in external biosecurity that can be easily resolved.
- » The main critical points identified on the farm for interaction with wildlife relate to external and internal fencing, the farm environment, vehicle management, and personnel management.
- » Wild boar, the main wild reservoir of ASF in Europe, is the main risk factor for introducing this virus into the farm: there are several attractive elements near and inside the farm (the pond, the leaking cooler and the smell of females in heat), its presence in the vicinity of the farm has been demonstrated through signs and the fencing has some weak points (access through the external fence permeable to wild boar, part of the internal fence not buried, possible appearance of underpasses due to runoff).
- » Direct contact between wild boar and domestic pigs is ruled out because wild boar would never have access to the interior of the sheds. However, these animals could roam around the farm and leave excretions (saliva, urine, or feces) in the corridor between sheds and inside the internal fence. The animals could subsequently come into contact with these excretions (if they were in the corridor between sheds) or employees could accidentally bring them inside the sheds.
- » There is also a risk of indirect interaction with other swine: the consumption of pork products in the farm's canteen. Even if they are consumed only in a specific location, they still represent a potential route for pathogens to enter the farm.
- » All recommendation for prevent the entry of ASF part of the implementation of a program of training comprehensive in subject of biosecurity for the workers and of certain modifications structural and design in the facilities. Various specific measures are proposed to correct the observed deficiencies, which must be maintained over time.

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Photographic annex

Exterior fencing: Overall, it is in good condition and non-permeable to wild ungulates, but vegetation at the base, potential crawl spaces (in the southern sector of the farm), and permeable access near the slurry pond limit its effectiveness. The photo at the bottom is an example of a vegetation-free fence.

Interior fencing: It is in good condition, but to make it non-permeable to wild ungulates, it would need to be anchored to the concrete base or the ground. Furthermore, the vegetation at the base can provide shelter for small animals. The last photo is an example of a fence anchored to the ground.

Signs of wild boar around the farm: A bathtub was found near the parking lot and footprints leading east from the fence.

Pond near the farm: Most of the perimeter is covered by typical vegetation and is inaccessible to wild ungulates, but there is a ramp where animals can descend to drink. The photo at the bottom shows a well fenced pond.

Leak in the maternity ward cooler: it could act as an attraction point of water for wildlife

RISK EVALUATION, DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF BIOSECURITY MEASURES AT THE WILDLIFE-POULTRY INTERFACE IN SPAIN

EXAMPLE 3

Caged Layer Farm

REPORT

Risk evaluation and proposition of biosecurity measures

SABIO
Sanidad y Biotecnología
Health and Biotechnology

World Organisation
for Animal Health

This real example has been developed by Health and Biotechnology Group of the National Institute on Wildlife Research (IREC) of the University of Castile-La Mancha/CSIC/JCCM.

Contents

RISK EVALUATION, DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF BIOSECURITY MEASURES AT THE WILDLIFE-POULTRY INTERFACE IN SPAIN

Caged layer farm

1. The importance of biosecurity in the prevention of highly and low pathogenic avian influenza outbreaks

2. Biosecurity with a focus on the wildlife livestock interface on layer farms

Methodology

3. Description of specific biosecurity program for layer farms

Farm description and identification of risk points

General characteristics of farm and surroundings

Wildlife presence and interaction with poultry

Map

Assessment and scoring of general wildlife-livestock-interface specific biosecurity risks

Proposed farm-specific biosecurity measures

Personnel governance

Reduction of attractiveness of farm premises for wildlife (wild birds)

Management of fencing and barriers to entrance into poultry barns (bird netting, etc.)

Management of water access

Management of carcass and other subproducts

4. Proposal of biosecurity measures (summary)

5. Annex: Biosecurity measure implementation

1. The importance of biosecurity in the prevention of highly and low pathogenic avian influenza outbreaks

Avian influenza virus (AIV) is one of the mayor threats to a poultry farm, both due to its direct impact (mortality and loss of productivity) and the necessity to cull positive flocks to stop the spread of the disease.

Between 2021 and 2024 Several billion poultry have been culled worldwide because of highly pathogenic avian influenza virus (HPAI) H5N1 outbreaks. Low pathogenic H5 or H7 avian influenza viruses once introduced into a flock have also a high risk to mutate to highly pathogenic genotypes through recirculation in the chickens of a flock thus requiring depopulation of the entire flock as a preventive measure. AIV is one of the most important respiratory contagious diseases of domestic poultry and other bird species, known for its rapid spread. The causative agent of AIV is a member of the genus influenza virus from the family Orthomixoviridea. Its segmented RNA and the lack of control for mutations during replication in host cells implicates continuous changes and reassortments of the virus. Only genus A viruses are known to cause a natural infection in birds and classified by the combinations of the (known) 19 (although 17 and 18 are yet only known in bats) hemagglutinin and 9 neuraminidase surface glycoproteins into numerous subtypes. Subtypes are also classified by their ability to cause disease in chickens and while most subtypes cause no or mild respiratory symptoms viruses belonging to h5 and H7 subtypes can mutate into versions that instead of replicating locally in the digestive or respiratory tract affect the whole organism and cause severe disease and extremely high mortality. With highly pathogenic subtypes mortality in a barn may reach 90-100% mortality while it may be between 30 and 40% or lower with low pathogenic subtypes. Nevertheless, with the current stamping out policy in the European Union detection of even seropositivity will lead to culling of the entire flock.

Wild aquatic birds, especially wild ducks, are thought to be the natural reservoirs of the low pathogenic avian influenza viruses but have in the recent past also been carriers and victims of highly pathogenic AIV H5N1. Passerines have been considered potential bridge species involved in AIV transmission between the natural reservoir and farms, and transmission has been experimentally confirmed with sparrows and starlings directly and through contamination of drinking water (Jones et al., 2015). In addition, detection of AIV RNA in ventilation shafts suggests these may also be a route of indirect airborne transmission of AIV into poultry barns (Elbers et al., 2022).

Recent studies have also shown that wild bird incursions even on farms on which birds are housed indoors are related to specific resources that make the premises attractive for wild birds, namely food, water and roosting possibilities (Sánchez Cano et al., 2024, Shriner & Root, 2020). Thus, biosecurity measures limiting entry of wild birds into barns but also their presence on farm premises are key to preventing entry and spread of avian influenza virus.

Biosecurity assessment at the Wildlife-Livestock Interface

Biosecurity (wildlife livestock interface) assessment at layer farms

1-Methodology

This biosecurity risk assessment is carried out in four phases:

1. Preparative study and data retrieval for each studied farm.
 - i) General information.
 - ii) Disease history:
 - Primary disease history and concerns
 - Records of Salmonella surveillance
 - Vaccination plan (if available)
 - iii) Maps.
2. Farm visit and on-site questionnaire, risk point inspection and wildlife access assessment.
 - i) Farm specific questionnaire:
 - General characteristics.
 - Personnel governance.
 - Farm management.
 - Biosecurity measures and challenges (Peripheral fence, anteroom, disinfection. Wildlife exclusion)
 - Identification of potential risk points.
 - ii) Risk point inspection:
 - Description of each risk point and categorization of associated risk)
3. Assessment of Wildlife Access and direct and indirect contact with poultry
 - i) Camera trapping
 - ii) Capture of birds, rodents and insects
 - iii) Samples for pathogen detection (wildlife, ambient)
4. Design and implementation of specific biosecurity measures (present report)
 - i) Sanitary control and movement of farm animals.
 - ii) Management of peripheral fence, entrances and vegetation (trees).
 - iii) Measures to separate wildlife & poultry/deter wildlife access.
 - iv) Management of water, feed and litter.
 - v) Management of carcasses and feed remains.
5. Monitoring of implementation and effectivity of biosecurity measures.
 - i) Summary of implemented measures.
 - Pictures.
 - Ambient samples.
 - ii) Evaluation of trends of pathogens of interest (if present) with field samples:
 - Red poultry mite

Biosecurity assessment at the Wildlife-Livestock Interface

- Salmonella
- Infectious Bronchitis virus IBV.

iii) Cost evaluation

Figure 2. Work program for assessment on individual farms

3. Description of specific biosecurity program for layer farms

3.1 Description of farm

General characteristics and farm management

Table 1. General information

Name	XXX
ID code	XXX
Municipality	XXX
Contact	XXX
Position	XXX
Telephone	
E-mail	

Table 2. General farm description.

Type	Indoor layer farm
Number of barns	10
Species	Layers and Japanese quail
Production system LAYERS	Modified cage system
Breed	Hyline Brown, Isa Brown, Hisex White
No. of Layers	600.000
Flocks	All in – all out single age barns
Feed	Farm-specific Feedmill
Production system	Raising of layer chicks from day 1 to week 19, single age barns
Egg treatment	On-site classification and packing system
Disease history	Red poultry mite, Infectious bronchitis, <i>Salmonella</i> in 2018/2019.
Production system Japanese Quail	Group cages
Breed	Japanese quail
No. birds	40.000

Biosecurity assessment at the Wildlife-Livestock Interface

Flocks	Single barn all-in all-out single age
Feed	Farm-specific feedmill
Disease history	NA
Other poultry	Free-range layer farm (60000 layers/30ha) of the same company at 11.2 km distance
Other livestock	Absent
Other domestica animals	cats

XXX is a family origin poultry farm founded in 1960. The farm is centred in egg production and houses 600.000 layers in 9 barns in modernized cage systems and 40.000 Japanese quail in a single barn for egg and meat production. The farm has its own feed mill and a barn on separate premises (500m distance) for raising layers from hatch until week 19. Layers are managed by barn as single age all-in- all-out flocks. The farm is located at approximately 2km from a small town close to a rural street. It is surrounded primarily by cereal crops (dry crop barley) and includes a small olive yard. No other livestock is present on the premises or surrounding fields. Several cats are present on the premises.

The farm counts with a perimetral fence and a disinfection arc and ditch at the main entrance. Another entrance towards the cereal fields closest to the sewage pond is a dirt road with no disinfection, as is a second entrance towards the egg classification centre. The fence is mostly well maintained and sufficient to not allow entrance to wild ungulates. During the first visit a file of American elm (*Ulmus americanus*) trees was present next to the entrance road close to one of the barns that was used as sleeping roost by spotless starlings (*Sturnus unicolor*).

Bird netting is present in ventilation shafts and windows of all barns. Nevertheless, house sparrows and occasionally pigeons are present inside barns.

The farm has a continuous low to high intensity of red poultry mite (RPM, *Dermanyssus gallinae*) infestation in at least two barns that is regularly treated with antiparasitic, especially in advanced egg production and when a reduction in production is observed. Monitoring of RPM to inform treatments is not in place.

During 2018/2019 the farm has had barn-specific Salmonella detections during fortnight voluntary controls and confirmatory official control in one individual layer barn, leading to exclusion, clearance and disinfection of the affected barn.

Despite vaccination several barns have suffered infectious bronchitis outbreaks that have negatively affected productivity.

Figure 3. Farm premises.

Risk points for wildlife -livestock interaction (direct & indirect)

While the potential for access by wild mammals (except rodents) is low, it is high for wild synanthropic birds. Presence of puddles of run-off water, spilled feed around silos, roosting opportunities and carcasses near manure transportation belts attracts birds from different orders including insectivorous and granivorous synanthropic songbirds that in turn can come into contact with waterfowl outside farm premises and act as bridge species for certain pathogens such as avian influenza virus, Coronaviruses including infectious bronchitis, Salmonella or the red poultry mite.

Direct contact of birds that enter the barns despite bird netting and indirect contact by contamination of feed with faeces are the most likely contact opportunities. Also the high density of insects (flies & mosquitoes) makes these potential mechanic or amplifying vectors.

Biosecurity assessment at the Wildlife-Livestock Interface

Figure 4 Risk assessment score (combined from questionnaire, field visits and one year trapping and sampling effort)

Table 3. Biosecurity risk assessment and categorization of risk of direct/indirect wildlife domestic layer interaction on indoor layer farms.

Dimension	Variable	Assessment category
Distance to other holdings	Distance to other holdings (1 kilometre is the threshold because it is the minimum distance between most farms according to Real Decreto 306/2020)	>1000m: 0
Perimetral fence	Fence permeability (fences are considered as permeable if the lower part of any section wasn't buried in soil or concrete)	Complete but locally permeable fence: 0.5
	Access permeability	Doors open during daylight: 0,5
Farm surroundings	Presence of crops	Presence of rain-fed cereal crops: 0,5
	Presence of forest patches	No:0
	Presence of water points	No:0
Farm premises	Presence of crops	Absence: 0
	Presence of trees	Yes:1
	Presence of water points	Yes: 1
Presence of wildlife on premises	Presence of wild birds on premises	Yes: 1
	Presence of wild birds in barns	Frequent: 1

Biosecurity assessment at the Wildlife-Livestock Interface

	Presence of other wildlife/signs	0: never
Animal replacement	Number of animal origins	0.5: 1 or 2 origins
	Number of animal entries	0.5: between 2 and 5 entries (barn specific and after raising barn)
Vehicle control	Vehicles entered inside the perimetral fence	1: yes
	Loading bay inside the perimetral fence	1: yes
	Carcass vehicles share the same entry road with the rest of vehicles	1: yes
	Manure vehicles shared the same entry road with the rest of vehicles	0: no
	Presence of an operational sanitary ditch	0: yes
Carrion processing	Carcasses were accessible for scavengers	1: yes
	Carcasses storage	1: simple containers
Manure management	Manure pits accessibility (for birds)	1: accessible
Water treatment	Water disinfection	0: yes
Feed management	Presence of feedstuff residues under silos	1: yes
Staff governance	Workers are shared with other holdings	0: no
	Presence of barriers between clean and dirty compartments in the changing room	1: no
	Presence of foot bath/shoe cleaner	0: yes

Biosecurity assessment at the Wildlife-Livestock Interface

Visitor control	Use of exclusive farm clothing by visitors	0: yes
	Compulsory registering for the visits	0: yes
Cleaning, disinfection and pest control	Presence of a cleaning and disinfection protocol	0: yes
	Presence of bird-proof and mosquito-proof nets	0.5: presence of bird-proof net
	Presence of a rodent control system	0,5: yes, but insufficient
	Insect control periodicity	0.5: at intervals ≥ 6 months
	Red poultry mite control	0.5: periodically based on infestation, no monitoring protocol

4. Proposal of biosecurity measures (summary)

General measures refer to the general farm management including non-wildlife related measures such as personnel governance, vehicle control and disinfection, while specific biosecurity measures refer to those aimed at reducing direct and indirect wildlife-poultry interactions.

1- Personnel governance

Reduce traffic of worker vehicles on farm premises and control contact of workers with wild birds or other domestic birds at least 48 hours before and after entering the farm premises. If possible, assign barn-specific workers

2- Disinfection and rodent/PRM control

Implementation of clean/dirty zone separation and handwashing in antechambers of barns. Increase rodent and insect control. Implement monthly monitoring of PRM at critical locations in barns and adjust treatments to PRM population data (earlier treatment will increase effectiveness).

3- Feed/water supply

Avoid spills of feed or water along the network and transfer between barns and around silos.

Biosecurity assessment at the Wildlife-Livestock Interface

4- Carcass and manure management

Increase frequency of carcass collection and maintain bird remains in tightly closing containers. Ensure manure collection at a distance from barns or of-premises. Avoid crossed routes of supply, feed, and egg-collection transports with

5- Wild bird access to premises vs direct/indirect contact

Reduce or eliminate vegetation that can act as roosts, reduce feed spill around silos as well as access to water in run-off puddles. Use wild bird deterrents on farm premises such as predator noises/silhouettes, ultrasound impulses.

6- Wild bird access to barns

Improve bird netting and implement double doors into barn antechambers and flaps and manure and egg transportation belts

Figure 4: Critical control points for wildlife domestic poultry interaction risk.

Biosecurity assessment at the Wildlife-Livestock Interface

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Biosecurity assessment at the Wildlife-Livestock Interface

Annex.

Follow up for biosecurity measure implementation (summary/examples)

- 1- Wildlife -poultry interface
 - Vegetation reduction: Trees (roost opportunities) removed
 - Reduction of feed/water spill
 - Carcass removal
 - Improved bird/insect netting
- 2- Personnel governance/vehicle control
 - parking for personnel moved outside farm premises
 - Different routes for egg collection, supply delivery and carcass/manure collection implemented

